

A Study on the Inherent Attributes of an Entrepreneur Engineer and their Challenges - A Case Study Analysis

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Abstract

The study focusses on the inherent qualities of an “engineering entrepreneur” who not only have to have the responsibility of managing a business enterprise but also, should have the capacity to face challenges that is confronted by them during the start of a new enterprise.

The study focusses on the adaptability and Risk and uncertainty managing skills of IBM as compared to APPLE which made IBM have an edge over APPLE. The findings reveal that eliminating risk is not possible though engineers are equipped with necessary knowledge-kit and skill-set to run an enterprise. They have to minimise It to optimise their business objective of bringing a technical idea into a reality.

Electronics and communication engineering education develops the necessary skill-set required to become an entrepreneur. It is the responsibility of an engineer to make it a reality. The invention made by an engineer can be used for a commercial purpose.

For eg: Samsung washing machine was equipped with waterfall effect while washing here, bringing waterfall effect is technology but using it for washing is business.

Introduction

The term entrepreneur is derived from the French word ‘entreprendre’ meaning ‘to undertake’. so the meaning of an entrepreneur is - ‘a person who is responsible for setting up a business or an enterprise’. He possesses skill, initiative and innovative ideas to set up a business. Entrepreneurship is a propensity of mind to take calculated risks with confidence to achieve a predetermined business or an industrial objective. it is a risk-taking ability of an individual coupled with correct decision-making.

Review of Literature

Engineer-Entrepreneur: combining technical knowledge with entrepreneurship education—the ISRAELI case study by MIRI YEMINI and JEHUDA HADDED discusses the engineer entrepreneur program in detail—this programme reflects a marked change from the regular educational paradigm. They believe that the program has succeeded in conveying the managerial and entrepreneurial side of the engineering profession.

Engineering and Innovation –An immersive start-up experience by THOMAS MILLER III, STEPHEN WAISH, SETH HOLLAR, ELAINE RIDEOUT; BERYL PITTMAN-has shown that engineering entrepreneur program has been helping engineering students become entrepreneurs.

Engineering Entrepreneurship—an example of a paradigm shift in engineering education by MR. CHRISTOPHER, J, CREED, DR ERIC M. SUUBERG, DR GREGORY P CRAWFORD-this paper describes technology –based entrepreneurship in which local “parent companies” provide seed ideas or concepts to student groups who use skill learned in the classroom.

5 reasons start-ups fail by DAVID SKOK-in his work “for entrepreneurs” mentions,

1. Market problems
2. Business model failure
3. Poor management team
4. Running out of cash
5. Product problems

AN ORGANISATIONAL PERSPECTIVE OF KNOWLEDGE COMMUNICATION IN DEVELOPING ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION FOR ENGINEERING STUDENTS- BY K, SUDHARSON, AHMED MUDDASSAR ALI, AND A.M. BELIEVE THAT- creativity and innovativeness are among the most essential attributes of graduates and also of successful entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurship or the process of starting a new venture, is one of the main roads to new technological innovations.

ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION—PUBLISHED BY IEEE-(8 AUTHORS) opine that the recent changes in the world and engineering present both challenges and opportunities to the engineering education. In this paper, eight authors present their view on teaching entrepreneurship to future engineers

Objectives

- To analyse the important qualities of an engineering entrepreneur as a leader in managing a business enterprise
- To make a comparative study of APPLE AND IBM
- To highlight on the challenges faced by start-up enterprises.

Objective 1

To analyze the important qualities of an Engineering Entrepreneur as a leader in managing a business enterprise

The following qualities has been identified as very important for the success of an enterprise

1. **Trust:** The Entrepreneur must trust his team. He has to select them with great caution. He has to repose confidence in them, and induce interest to deliver tasks to the best of their ability.
2. **Honesty:** As an Engineer, you should be honest even in a bad situation. Projects may fail if an Entrepreneur is dishonest.

3. **Effective Communication Skills:** Both written and oral communication should be good for an Engineer. Engineers deal with a lot of people within and outside the organization. They need to clearly communicate the problems, solutions to both their team and outsiders. Otherwise it may lead to confusions and people may be reluctant to accept your product. It is very important to communicate clearly in the language that people would understand.
4. **Team Work:** You need your team workers to work on your goals to make it a success. Being a leader, an Entrepreneur has to encourage, empower and empathize his team members. They should be a role model. This is a very important trait that will contribute to your success as you are playing a dual role of a manager and an Entrepreneur. The resources of the company have to be used in an effective manner.
5. **Open Minded:** An Engineer must think out of box. He / She has to analyse the repercussions or impact of this product/service on the society. An Engineer must not just focus on immediate needs but should have a big picture regarding cost, competition, wastage and earnings. Business plan should be accurately presented. Open minded also means he should be capable of making adjustments and changes in project plans.
6. **Facing Uncertainty:** There are two types of risks, insurable risks and non-insurable risks for an Entrepreneur. Risks that can be anticipated, foreseen and insurable should be insured. For eg: accidents. Non-insurable risks are called uncertainties. An Entrepreneur cannot eliminate risk but can minimize it. He has to take calculated risks in business. It is important for an Engineer to think ahead and identify possible problems that confronts business.
7. **Managing Risks:** Project plans are not always perfect. It is a regular phenomenon that problems and turning points arise anytime. An Engineer has to effectively manage this and prevent it from happening again. So, he has to build a team which has competent skills and be helpful.
8. **Set Challenging but Realistic Goals:** Challenging goals may impress everyone but yield incomplete results if not achieved and will further bring down the confidence levels. It does not benefit both the company and the Engineer. Realistic goals are achievable. So, it is easy to persuade the team to pursue them. The goals should be positive, measurable, pragmatic and tangible and should have a time-frame.
9. **Reduce Complexities:** Complexities in understanding, implementing a project should be reduced. It is better that your team know about the plan, schedules and budget of the project and also the risks involved in it. To avoid complexities, it is necessary that the Engineer should explain a task and goals in simple terms so that it is understood easily.
10. **Action-Oriented:** there is a lag between strategy and implementation. Implementing a decision or action is always a problem. Sometimes an Entrepreneur alone has to deal with the problem. If you anticipate a disaster you should take immediate and appropriate action.
11. **Team Building:** If you want to continue to be a leader, there will be a challenge. Every part of the team will play an important role in every project and team requires proper guidance and direction from the leader. Team leader knows the strength and weaknesses of each member. He has to delegate tasks according to their ability.

What makes Engineers Great Entrepreneur?

Being ‘Entrepreneur’ is one of the options available to Engineer when they seek job opportunities. Engineers can be better or great Entrepreneurs for the following reasons

1. **Analytical Skills:** Engineers possess analytical skills. Engineers are trained to think logically and usually follow a methodology to find useful solutions.
2. **Optimism:** The technical skills possessed by an Engineer helps him to persist in the face of difficulty. As he is a science student basically, they will have the quality to think and act rationally. They are result oriented and optimistic.

3. **Knowledge:** An Engineer is always reading to search a solution for a problem. He will increase his knowledge base and ensure that he taps to use it at the right time, when a new product / service is developed

Objective 2

- To make a comparative study of APPLE and IBM on their success edge.
- Adopted parent Paul who was a mechanic helped Steve jobs in garage electronics and this was the basis for him to reconstruct the field of electronics and gradually this turned into his hobbies which lead to the path of inventing and creating something new
- Jobs always had a smart and an intelligent mind. During his school days he was admired for carrying out innovative experiments.
- He got associated with Steve wozniak who in future becomes his partner in “Apple”. The commonality between them was that both were interested in electronics. After this he was a mix of so many things.
- He joined Reed College in Portland and dropped out. Next he took up calligraphy. In 1974, got a job as a video designer. Suddenly took the spiritual path in India. But he was in the continuous touch with wozniak.
- With him, he started “Apple Computers” in 1976.As the journey started, Steve jobs started making machines which are smaller, cheaper, user-friendly and innovative.
- Competition with IBM hit back Apple as it incurred huge losses.
- Why people fancied IBM- Apple Computers run as Macintosh OS X(older apples use an earlier OS version such as OS9)
- While IBM pc’s run as a Microsoft windows xp or latest windows 7
- Apple Computers are generally marketed to the arts industry where as IBM pc’s are generally marketed to businesses-Most accounting software will run as Microsoft based operating system.
- Microsoft based computers are generally known for their value for money, whereas Apple computers are generally overpriced, but providing a much better user experience.
- However start –ups enjoy some advantage which is not available to established entrepreneurs they are
- Success story:start-ups are not burdened with success history.
- INNOVATION IS INDISPENSABLE:start-ups should not have a credibility gap. Innovations should be compelling, only then will people become customers.
- CLOSER TO CUSTOMER NEEDS: Start-ups tap the needs make innovations and succeed. In the early stage start-ups,talk to everyone and learn about their needs. This creates great environment for innovations as they identify market needs and produce accordingly.

An Engineer thinks of Starting an Enterprise as

Every engineer who has invented some new technology feels like taking this to the market as an entrepreneur

Same Skills

Engineers and entrepreneurs share same skills. Infact many leaders and entrepreneurs are engineers. To quote some of them, bill gates, Carlos shim and others.

Both engineers and entrepreneurs take a tremendous amount of risk in their work.

Engineers make great entrepreneurs because they bring a skillset to the start-ups and are capable of solving big problems.

Objective 3

To highlight on the challenges faced by start-ups

1. **NO MARKET RESEARCH-** It’s more a ‘gut feeling’ or so called passion rather than conducting a thorough market research to establish the need for product.
2. **MENTORSHIP CRISIS:** Traditional managers are not equipped to become entrepreneurs. they do not have experienced mentors in their field to help start-ups so that they eliminate danger before they occur.
3. **COMPETITION WITH BRANDS:** If a substitute already exists, this new product which is a baby has to face competition with established brands.
4. **TALENT AND SKILL:** Start-ups cannot afford talented and skilled people. They are expected to possess multi skill.
5. **POLICY OF THE GOVERNMENT:** The policies and programmes of govt are ever changing. They do not have a long term start-up road map.
6. **NO EXPERIMENTS BEFORE LAUNCH:** Experiments can provide answers to many questions which are very essential for start-ups.
7. **TEAM WORK:** Due to lack of experience, and trusted resources good team building does not happen initially.
8. **BUILDING CASTLES IN THE AIR:** Success lies in skilful execution. Ideas can build castles in air but is it possible to build blocks of bricks to build castle.
9. **INSUFFICIENT INFORMATION ON MARKETING STRATERGIES IN INDIA:** In India, each state is different in food habits, technical standards etc. so it is necessary to identify the required strategy to market products.

Findings

Analytical skills, knowledge and team building ability is very important for an entrepreneur. Capacity to identify like-minded people who can work for a common goal like Steve Jobs and Woznaik are important. It is still important to anticipate turning points causing uncertainty in a business, minimise it if not completely eliminate them.

Suggestions

An entrepreneur should have a definite focus and have all the qualities mentioned above to establish himself as a leader.

Start-up’s should not ignore market research. Concerned dealers of the product, manufacturers, should be consulted before deciding on the manufacture of the product. It is not sufficient if you are technically sound, you should possess marketing skills also.

Engineering education plays an important role in success of entrepreneurs under this domain.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that engineering domain promise technical expertise in designing a product but an engineer should possess vital qualities of risk and uncertainty bearing and take the help of marketing department to establish his enterprise and produce the product. This is possible by educating them in this regard.